

GENDER POLICY MONITORING AND EFFECTIVENESS ASSESSMENT.

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As everyone knows, in accordance with the resolution No. 70 of the United Nations General Assembly adopted at the Summit on Sustainable Development held in September 2015, as well as in order to organize systematic work on the consistent implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals of the UN Global Agenda in the period up to 2030, the Republic of Uzbekistan The Cabinet of Ministers adopted a decision on "Measures for the implementation of national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development until 2030". , it is necessary to ensure the full and effective participation of women and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and social life. In addition, this goal includes the introduction of gender equality principles in the process of adoption of State programs at different levels of the state. In recent years, efforts to ensure gender equality and increase the role of women in social and political life have been carried out in several directions:

- improvement of legislation on women's rights;
- improvement of the institutional foundations of women's protection;
- raising awareness of the population about gender equality and women's rights;
- train officials responsible for ensuring their compliance in law enforcement practice on the basis of relevant legal norms.

Uzbekistan has adopted a number of legislative documents, including decrees and decisions of the President on ensuring women's rights, in particular, on gender equality and protecting women from violence and oppression, on strengthening the status of women's entrepreneurship. need That is, since 2017, the activity of part-time departments in various specialties has been restored in most higher educational institutions. This form of education allows young women to obtain higher education without compromising childcare and other family responsibilities.

Taking this opportunity, I consider it appropriate to quote President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis in June 2019: "I am very concerned about the stereotype that has appeared in the minds of our people. Usually we respect a woman first of all as a mother, a guardian of the family fortress. This is certainly true. But today, every woman should be not just an

observer, but also an active and proactive participant in the democratic changes taking place in the country."

On this day, at the invitation of the President, for the first time in the history of the country, a woman - Tanzila Norboyeva - was elected as the chairman of the Senate. It is known that Ms. Norboyeva worked as the Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Chairman of the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan. As for the legislative measures in this area, in order to further improve the legal basis for ensuring and protecting women's rights in Uzbekistan, in September 2019, "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" and "Protection of women from oppression and violence" Laws on making" were adopted. Almost all UN agencies, including the United Nations Development Program, the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA), the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, the United Nations Office on Narcotic Drugs and Crime, and the International Organization for Migration have submitted their comments and suggestions on these two laws. they gave

As for institutional measures on gender equality, at the same time, a new Committee on Women and Girls and Gender Equality issues was established within the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is engaged in harmonizing international standards in the national legislation on ensuring women's rights and eliminating any form of discrimination. In addition, in order to further strengthen the guarantees and support of labor rights, to help victims of domestic violence, the rehabilitation and adaptation of victims of violence and the prevention of suicide, the Republican Center and the Center for Women and Girls Entrepreneurship, "Oila" under the Government new structures such as a scientific and practical research center were established.

Important changes have taken place in the field of monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of gender policy on the site www.gender.stat.uz by introducing additional 54 gender indicators. Not only the guidelines adopted here, but also their compliance with international obligations and standards, and their timely and accurate implementation on the ground are of great importance. In this sense, efforts to ensure the full and effective participation of women at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and social life are consistent. need to continue. Systematic monitoring of the implementation of the gender strategy, general coordination, prompt consideration and resolution of problematic issues that hinder the development of the sector, involving official state bodies, mass media, non-governmental non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil

society of Uzbekistan It is carried out by the Commission on Gender Equality of the Republic.

Monitoring of the implementation of the Gender Strategy is carried out on the basis of indicators of the evaluation of the activities of the competent bodies on the timely, high-quality and complete implementation of the activities provided for in the Gender Strategy.

The reports prepared on the results of the monitoring of the implementation of the gender strategy were considered at the meeting of the Commission on Ensuring Gender Equality of the Republic of Uzbekistan and at the meetings of the Committee on Women and Girls and Gender Equality of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. will be released.

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